

A STUDY OF CUSTOMER PREFERENCE AND SATISFACTION TOWARDS VARIOUS CELL PHONE SERVICE PROVIDERS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UDUMALPET TALUK

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Introduction:

A customer is an individual who purchase or has the capacity to purchase goods and services offered for sale by marketing institutions in order to satisfy personal or household needs, wants or desires. According to a statement made by Mahatma Gandhi, 'customer refers to the following, "A customer is the most important visitor on our premises. He is not dependent on us. We are dependent on him. He is not an outsider to our business. He is part of it. We are not doing him a favour by serving him. He is doing us a favour by giving us an opportunity to do so". So customer is like the blood of our business and also a satisfied customer is a word of mouth advertisement of a product / services.

Market:

The term market is derived from Latin Word 'Mercatus', which means 'to trade' that is purchasing and selling of goods. It also means merchandise truth place of business. According to Pyle, "Market includes both place and region in which buyers and sellers or in free competition with one another".

Marketing:

Marketing includes all the impacts involved in the exchange process transferring the possession and ownership of goods or services from the producer to the ultimate customer's

Customer Satisfaction:

Every human being is a customer of different produces. If there is no customer, there is no business. Therefore, customer satisfaction is very important to every business person. According to Philip Kotler customer satisfaction is defined on, "personal feeling of pleasure resulting from comparing a product's pursued performance in relation to his /her expectations". Customer attitude measurements are taken on either potential buries or existing client's buries in order to identify their characteristics. Why should the competent market engineer conduct customer research? Customer's survey scan provides the researcher with a wealth of information, valuable of the marketing function. Detailed information regarding the customer in a market will provide the basic platform for all marketing decisions. Marketing decision maker needs descriptive information about the total potential unit and dollar sales in each segment. Perhaps the most important one is that a seller need to be aware of the relevant objective and need of customer and how their objectives might best be served by the products.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the evaluation of cell phones with particular reference to India.
- ✓ To study the Socio Economic background of customers.
- ✓ To ascertain the attributes which influences the customer's in selecting a particular cell phone services provider.
- ✓ To study the customer's satisfaction towards different cell phone service providers in Udumalpet Taluk.
- ✓ To assess the problems faced by the cell phone users in Udumalpet Taluk.
- ✓ To offer valuable suggestions to improve the services of cell phones in Udumalpet Taluk.

Need of the Study:

Exchange of information becomes the necessity of life to a common man. In the modern world an individual tends to communicate anything to everything right from the place where he/she stands. Even while riding vehicle he / she wants communicate within a fraction of second at quick speed with clear voice, without any disturbance. Like line crossing, out of order, etc. most of which lack in the connection given by the department of tele-communication. Cell phones emerges as a boon quench such a thirst, the by providing facilities, which a common man cannot imagine. Though cell phone industry has its origin the recent past and the growth has been excellent. Day by day many new competitors enter the market with new attractive schemes, provide additional facilities, add new features to existing ones, reduce the charges her incoming and outgoing

calls, introduce varieties of handsets, models a healthy competition that benefits the subscribers. Hence in this context, it is important to study the functioning of cellular phone services, utilization of their services by the customer and problems faced by them.

Scope of Study:

The present study is confined to Udumalpet Taluk and it is decided to consider Airtel, Aircel and etc. cell phone service rendered to the customers. In Udumalpet there are various cellular services available such as Airtel, Aircel and etc. but the cellular services has been selected to study the customer's satisfaction in it is the most popular private cellular services. The main objectives of this study is to analyze the customers satisfaction and problems faced by Airtel, Aircel, etc., cellular services in Udumalpet city has been taken for the current research work.

Statement of Problem:

In our country the growth of service marketing especially mobile phone industry is still in its infancy stage, as compared to the industrially advanced countries. It is for the fact that the economy of our country has been in the developing stage. There are various mobile phones services provider's in our country and they are playing an essential role in fulfilling the needs of the customers. Now-a-days, the customers are more dynamic. Their taste, needs and preference can be changing as per current scenario. Hence the development of cellular industry mainly depends on the customer satisfaction. However the following questions may arise regarding customer satisfaction.

- ✓ Does the cell industry satisfy the social responsibility?
- ✓ What are all expectations by the customer's regarding service provided by the cell phone service provider?
- ✓ Whether the service provided by cell phone industry is satisfying the customers?
- ✓ Are the facilities available adequate to satisfy the customers?

Research Methodology:

Search of knowledge. A careful investigation or enquiry. A systematic effort to gain new knowledge. Those are called a "Research" Research is a movement of knowledge from known to unknown from the available place to the required place. According to Cliffordwode, "Defining and re-defining problems formulating the hypothesis or solutions. Collecting, organizing and evaluating data. Making detections and reaching conclusions to determine whether fit the formulating the hypothesis" The Purpose of research to find out solutions to the problem, which has not been discovered by anybody.

Research Methods: Those methods which are used by the researcher during the course of studying are research problem are termed on research methods.

Research Methodology: The research methodology, not only the research methods are but also consider the logic behind the methods. They are in the contest of our research studied. And explain why we are using a particular method or techniques and we are not using others.

Descriptive Research Design: It includes surveys, and facts finding enquires of different kinds. The man or purpose of descriptive research is description of state of affairs on it exists at present. The main character of this method is that the researcher has no control throw over the variables. He can report what has happen or what is happening.

Nature of Data: In this study primary and secondary data are used.

Collection of Data: Primary data: The data were collected from the respondents through the distribution of questionnaire. Secondary data: Secondary data refers to data that was collected by someone other than the user. Information collected through materials, books, magazines where ever suitable for the purpose of completing the study.

Tools Used:

- ✓ Percentage
- ✓ Chi square
- ✓ ANNOVA

Area of the Study: This study covers Udumalpet Taluk only.

Sample Size: The sample size of this study is 100.

Hypothesis of the Study: On the basis of review of previous studies and on the basis of observation made during our collection of data, the following null hypothesis was formed. There is no significant association between personal variables such as age, gender, educational qualifications, monthly income, marital status, size of the family and their awareness level of customers and different cell phone services providers.

- ✓ There is significant relationship between gender and level of satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between marital status and level of satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between educational qualification and level of satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between occupation and level of satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between monthly income and level of satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between service providers and level of satisfaction.

- ✓ There is no significant relationship between use of cell phone and level of satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between type of connection and level of satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between factors and opinion.

Limitations of the Study: Though the detailed investigation is made in the present study, it has got the following limitations.

- ✓ This study is restricted only to the Udumalpet Taluk. So, the results may not be applicable to other areas.
- ✓ This study is based on the prevailing customer's satisfaction. But the customer's satisfaction may change according to time, fashion, technology development, etc
- ✓ As per the population of the study is huge, the researcher has taken only 100 sample respondents from each service providers.

Review of Literature:

R. Sarika and Lohana (2012) in their article titled, "Customer Respond and Satisfaction against Marketing Strategies of Selected Cellular Service Providers in Handed City" have analyzed that in the today's competitive world is communication plays a very important role. The client does not want to miss any of his calls.

D. Srinivasa Prasad and S. Gangadhara Rama Rao (2012) in their article entitled, "Land Line Consumer Problems and Perceptions on Telecom Services: A Study on Bharat Sanchar Nigam Limited" have analysed that the telecom services have been recognized the world-over as an important tool for socioeconomic development for a nation and hence telecom infrastructure is treated as a crucial factor to realize the socio-economic objectives. BSNL is a wholly a Government of India undertaking, which provides the largest share of telecom services on fixed line networks in the country.

S. Vishnuvarthani (2013) in her article entitled "Consumers' Awareness and Preference for Mobile Phone Services at Erode City" has pointed out that telecommunication is one of the most important growing service sectors in India. It plays an inevitable role in today's busy world. The telecommunication includes both mobile communication and fixed telephony lines.

Evaluation of Cellular Phone:

Profile of Study Area: The municipality was established in 1918 and upgraded to second grade municipality in 1970. It was declared as a first grade municipality in 1979 and further upgrades to selection grade municipality in 1984. The extent of the municipality is 7.41 km² of which 6.582 km² is urban and 0.828 km² is rural. The city was part of Coimbatore district until 2008 when it became part of the newly formed Tirupur district, a change which was opposed by the residents. The town, in the 1980s and 1990s, had a developed spinning industry but it has since declined due to labor shortages and other labor related issues. There are paper manufacturing plants located alongside the Amaravathi River. The surrounding areas has seen a surge in windmill installations because of the location of the town across the Palghat Gap.

History of Cellular Telephony in India: Initially Department of Telecommunications (DoT) was the only monopoly operator in the country. Telecommunication sector was recognized by the Government of India as one of the few basic infrastructure sectors for the country. Under the Government policy of economic liberalization, privatization and competition in India, private sectors have been allowed to enter the public telecommunication field (where Government was a monopoly). In 1992 telecommunication sector in India was liberalized to bridge the gap through government spending and to provide additional resources for the nation's telecom target. The objective of the reform was making the telecommunications within the reach of all, thereby achieving universal service, covering all villages and bringing the telecommunication services to the world standard, while protecting the defense and security needs of the country. In 1993 the telecom industry got an annual foreign investment of Rs 20.6million. In 1994 license for providing cellular mobile services was granted by the Government of India for the Metropolitan cities of Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata and Chennai Initially Cellular mobile services were duopoly (i.e. not more than two cellular mobile operators could be licensed in each telecom circle), under affixed license fee. In 1995, government opened up 19 more telecom circles and issued mobile licenses To regulates and settles disputes Telecom Regulatory Authority of India was set up in 1997 and in 1999 National Telecom Policy was announced by the Government of India. In order to speed up the development of the telecom sector, all telecom services were opened up for private sector participation. Unrestricted entry is allowed in the basic services, national and international long distance service, in global mobile personal communication by satellite (GMPCS) service, VSAT and Public Mobile Radio Trunked Service(PMRTS).All telecom sectors under DoT was handed over to new public Sector Undertaking viz, Bharat Sanchar Nigam Limited (BSNL) which was registered under Company's Act in 1stOctober 2005. BSNL covers the entire country except Delhi and Mumbai Metros which are under Mahanagar Telephone Nigam Limited (MTNL).

Analysis and Interpretation:

Simple Percentage:

Composition of Respondents on the Basis of Gender Status:

S.No	Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Male	50	50
2	Female	50	50
Total		100	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

Table 4.1 shows that the gender respondents out of 100 respondents, 50 of the respondents are male and remaining 50 respondents are female.

Chi-Square:

Chi- Square Analysis on the Relationship between Age and Satisfaction with Regarding the Cell Phone Service Provider:

Age	High	Moderate	Low	Total
Upto 20	2	22	1	25
21-30	15	32	13	64
31-40	0	5	0	5
Above 40	1	6	3	10
Total	18	65	17	100

O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
2	4.5	-2.5	6.25	1.39
15	10.8	4.2	17.64	1.63
0	0.9	-0.9	0.81	0.90
1	1.8	-0.8	0.64	0.36
22	16.25	5.75	33.06	2.03
32	39	-7	49.00	1.26
5	3.25	1.75	3.06	0.94
6	6.5	-0.5	0.25	0.04
1	4.25	-3.25	10.56	2.49
13	10.2	2.8	7.84	0.77
0	0.85	-0.85	0.72	0.85
3	1.7	1.3	1.69	0.99
Total				11.65

Number of Degree of Freedom: $ndf = (row-1)(column-1)(3)(2)=6$

Table value of χ^2 at 5% level of significant = 13.65

Conclusion:

H_0 is accepted since the calculated value of $\chi^2(11.65)$ less than the table value of $\chi^2(13.65)$ Hence there is no significant relationship between level of satisfaction and age.

ANOVA Table:

Attributes	Aware	Neutral	Unaware	Total
Monthly Rental Charges	5	3	1	9
Charges For Cell Phone To Land Lines	6	2	3	11
Signal Of Tower Networking	9	8	2	19
Regular Scheme	5	6	0	11
Festival Scheme	4	5	0	9
Rate Cutter	6	3	2	11
Call Charges	9	3	0	12
SMS Charges	4	6	1	11
Roaming Charges	2	1	4	7
Total	50	37	13	100

Sources: Primary Data

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares (SS)	Degrees of Freedom (V)	Mean of Squares (MS)	F
Columns A	78.301	2	39.1505	39.1505/4.357=8.986
Rows B	29.61	8	37.0125	37.0125/4.357=8.495
Balance AB (Interaction)	69.719	16	4.357	
Total	177.63	26		

Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between factors and opinion.

H₁: There is significant relationship between factors and opinion.

DS-Degrees of Freedom SS-Sum of Squares MSS-Mean Sum of Squares F-Frequency

Table Value:

Table Value for (2, 16) degree of freedom at 5% level of significance is 3.63

Table Value for (8, 16) degree of freedom at 5% level of significance is 2.59

Inference:

Calculated value (8.986) is more than the table value (3.63) H₀ hypothesis is accepted. Hence that there is no significant variance in products attributes and the respondents opinion about the products.

Findings Suggestions and Conclusions:

Introduction: The main objective of the study was to study the Customer's Preference and Satisfaction towards Various Cell Phone Service Providers. The other objective of the study were to analysis the problems faced by the Customer's to study the relationship between personal factors and the satisfactory level of the respondents. The present study was based on survey method. Primary data was collected from the respondents those who are using cell phone services products in Udumalpet Taluk with help of questionnaire. The secondary data was collected from various Journals, Internet, Magazines, Books and research report.

Findings:

Percentage Analysis:

- ✓ Majority of the respondents are up to 20 years of age group (60%), 21-30 years age group (51.56%), 31-40 years age group (80%), 41 and above years (40%)
- ✓ Majority of the respondents were unmarried (70%)
- ✓ Majority of the respondents educational qualification are under graduate level (65%)
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are student (40%)
- ✓ Majority of the respondents purchase cell phones for their personal use (85%)
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are using both schemes in Airtel prepaid (55% and 8%)
- ✓ Majority of the respondent's using both incoming and outgoing facilities (74%)
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are highly satisfied with the performance of Airtel service provider (50%).
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are highly satisfied by the periodical offers provided by Airtel service providers (56%).
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are highly satisfied with Airtel outgoing call charges (60%).
- ✓ Majority of the Respondents Attitude towards the Importance of Cell Phones become Necessity (63%).
- ✓ Majority of the respondents spent Rs.1000 per month.

Chi Square-Test:

- ✓ H₀ is accepted since the calculated value of X²(11.65) less than the table value of X² (13.65) Hence there is no significant relationship between level of satisfaction and age.
- ✓ H₀ is accepted since the calculated value of X²(1.57) less than the table value of X² (5.99) Hence there is no significant relationship between level of satisfaction and gender.
- ✓ H₀ is accepted since the calculated value of X²(1.30) less than the table value of X² (5.99) hence there is no significant relationship between level of satisfaction and marital status.
- ✓ H₀ is accepted since the calculated value of X² (8.09) less than the table value X² (12.59) hence there is no significant relationship between level of satisfaction and educational qualification.

ANOVA:

- ✓ Calculated value (8.986) is more than the table value (3.63) H₀ hypothesis is accepted. Hence that there is no significant variance in products attributes and the respondents opinion about the products.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Airtel should try to attract old peoples also.
- ✓ 75% of the peoples are unaware about the various services rendered by their service provider. So the service providers Try to make awareness of their customers services to their customers.
- ✓ BSNL, Reliance, Tata indicom should attract the customers by reducing their price.
- ✓ BSNL, Reliance customers are highly dissatisfied about the performance of the service provider. So they should try to add some advanced features towards their services. Airtel should try to increase their after sales services.

Conclusion:

This is an information era significance of information cannot be over emphasized. This study attempts to find out the satisfaction of CUSTOMER regarding cell phone service providers. This decade, most of the peoples using cell phones. So, service providers are increasing in more level. So service provider are should over come another one's competition. So, it leads to adding new features, schemes, periodical offers to their service. So, the CUSTOMERS get maximum benefit from their service provider. Now-a-days, cell phones are

very necessity to all. Because, it's give safety to the men and women also. And no person are feel cell phones are luxury one.

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